

Seminar thesis II

'Longing for home' – Nostalgia in the last decade of Martinů's life.

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Introduction

The connection of Bohuslav Jan Martinů (1890-1959) with that of his homeland was exceptionally strong despite the fact that he spent most of his life outside of it. During his initially planned 'brief' sojourn in Paris he visited his native town of Polička only during the summer months to compose and to teach music, and, after leaving Paris for New York in 1940; he never returned to the country of his birth. His body of work attests to this connection also, with many of his compositions containing extra musical folk elements from his native Bohemia. In this essay I will endeavour to find direct musical ties with that of his later period in relation to the music of the present-day Czech Republic. I will then look at the connection with Janáček and assess their musical relationship. I will also look at Martinů's lasting influence and try to examine his place in twentieth century music.

First, however, I will look at how Martinů's style came to be, through the various different influences which he gathered during his life and career.

Martinů's artistic development constituted the influence of many different styles and stylistic periods.

He began his studies at the Prague conservatory whilst playing 2nd violin in the Czech Philharmonic. It was there that he came into contact with the music of Czech composers such as Antonín Dvořák, Bedřich Smetana and Josef Suk. A fascination with the baroque concerto grosso gave him a particular reverence for the *Brandenburg concerti* of Bach and the music of Corelli which he considered as being the epitome of form. This led to the work *Dvojkoncert (Double Concerto)* for two String Orchestras Piano and Timpani (Halbriech catalogue number 271).

He was also interested in Bohemian and Moravian folk song and this contributed to developing a legacy of folk miniatures, the use of native poetry and depiction of folk scenery in his work.

These, in conjunction with his love of the French impressionistic music of Albert Roussel and Claude Debussy, played an important role in his inspiration and development.

Paris proved to be a very important influence on his work, not just musically and culturally also.

When not attending classes with Roussel, Martinů enjoyed perusing the book stores of Paris' streets searching for anything to read. A trait which he inherited from his days as a young boy reading in St. James' tower in Polička. The Parisian Czech colony on La Rue de Vanves also gave him a particularly strong cultural stimulus, with multiple arts consisting of the drawings and paintings of Jan Zrzavý, František Kupka and Rudolf Kundera, the writings of Vítěslav Nezval and Jiří Muchal and music of his Prague companion; Jan Novák and Janáček's piano student Rudolf Firkušný.

He also took particular notice of the Stravinsky influence in Paris and among his favourite works were *Histoire du Soldat*, *Petrushka*, *Les Noces* and *Le Sacre du Printemps*. Perhaps the rhythmic restlessness and unpredictability evident in his work can be related to Stravinsky's own technique or indeed, as a double influence of Jazz. Jazz at that time in Paris was also influential in Martinů's rhythmic development and he displayed originality in such works as *Le Revue du Cuisine (Kuchňská Revue)* (H. 161), *Le Jazz* (H.168) and his *Jazz suite* (H. 172).

Renaissance madrigals and the influence of the English tradition inspired him to write *Eight Czech madrigals* (H.278), *Five Czech madrigals* (H.321) and *Four Madrigals (part-song book)* (H. 380) on folk texts. This influence of renaissance madrigals could be the reason why the 6th symphony, titled: *Fantaisies Symphoniques* (H. 343) contains so much polyphonic writing.

Also, an interesting parallel can be found in the opening of the first movement, where there is evidence of polyphonic, or more specifically, evidence of 'micropolyphonic' writing, which is often connected to the works of his contemporary of 30 years: Ligeti, György (1923-2006).

This technique of writing is identified in Ligeti's orchestral work *Atmosphères* and is elaborated on by the Oxford dictionary of music.

"*Atmosphères* (1961), which is almost a single cloud, drifting through different regions of colour, harmony and texture, whether in the form of sustained tones or of what he called 'micropolyphony',

consisting of dense weaves of canons at the unison, in which the lines move at different speeds and are not separately identifiable.”¹

It is also identified and described in connection with Ligeti’s requiem.

“Ligeti’s Requiem consists of just four sections, ‘Introitus’, ‘Kyrie’, ‘De Judicii Sequentia’ and ‘Lacrimosa’: the third of these features violently disjunct vocal lines, with words and syllables split between different voice-parts. In the Kyrie, on the other hand, what Ligeti calls ‘micropolyphony’, fast-moving canonic patterns in the voices, is set against a slow-moving chromatic orchestral background.”²

This shows that Martinů was quite ahead of his time, with *Atmosphères* being composed in 1961 two years after Martinů's death. The micropolyphonic writing of the first movement of his Sixth Symphony can be described using the same terms; Quickly moving, closely spaced independent lines which blend into a single sonority made up of smaller more complicated parts.

Both composers shared substantial interest in the music of Claude Debussy (1862-1928) which provides an important link in understanding their styles.

Whilst in New York, the prominent conductor Serge Koussevitsky requested Martinů to write a symphony for the Boston Symphony orchestra. The first of 6 symphonies to be exact. The sixth being the most distinctive mark of his late style. This symphony (as mentioned earlier) exhibits strong influential traits from its predecessors and, nearing the end of Martinů's life, not only contains influences of previous mentioned artists but also bears resemblance of the music of Leoš Janáček and more specifically with the occurrence of the Moravian cadence in the Finale of *Taras Bulba* which appears as a unifying motif in *Fantaisies Symphoniques*.

Apart from this Janáček connection which I will investigate later, Martinů's love of his home country can be attested to other works, most all those composed in the last twenty years of his life, such as the folk cantata with texts by fellow Polička native Miloslav Bureš; *Otvírání Studáněk*

1 Paul Griffiths. "Ligeti, György." (Grove Music Online. Oxford Music Online.)

2 Theodore Karp et al. "Requiem Mass." (Grove Music Online. Oxford Music Online.)

(H.354), duets on Moravian folk poetry; *Petrklíč* (H. 348), the folk balet *Špalíček* (H214), and its variant on Moravian folk songs for Piano and Voice *Nový Špalíček* (H.288) which was dedicated to the then exiled foreign minister Jan Masaryk.

Martinů was also so fond of his home town of Polička that he carried a frame with a photograph of St. James' Tower wherever he stayed.

Whilst in America during world war two, Martinů received news as to the fate of the village of Lidice in western Bohemia, which had most of its population murdered and transported to concentration camps in conjunction with having the entire town levelled by the Nazis, in reprisal for the assassination of the SS officer Reinhard Heydrich.

Martinů (amongst other composers), sought to continue the memory of the village in a new composition to be titled *Memorial to Lidice* (H. 296) which was premiered in New York in 1943.

Similar to Janáček in the use tragic dramatic content in music, a connection (although on a much smaller scale) can be found with the Piano sonata 1. X. 1905 *Z Ulice (From the Street)* which depicts the death of a young man named František Pavlík who was bayoneted during a protest for a Czech university in Brno.

Janáček uses a two-movement sonata for solo Piano to represent this to great effect.

Martinů and Janáček

Martinů was quite sparse in his mention of Janáček, although, in his letters to Zdeněk Zouhar³ he mentions his desire to obtain the former's collection of Moravian Songs.

“Now, if it isn't too much trouble for you (Zdeněk Zouhar), what I would actually like to have is Janáček, namely, if I am not mistaken, the second volume of Janáček's Moravian Songs published by the Czech academy, which contains religious songs.”⁴ Further on, he states that he needs the volume in order to find a text for his *Field Mass* (Halbriech number 279).

“I am to write something like a Field Mass for the Dutch male choir who have fallen in love with the mass and learned to sing it in Czech, and I suppose I would be able to find the text I need in the Janáček.”⁵

He also reflects on Janáček's opinions on harmony and harmonic timing in comment to the collection of Moravian folk songs in his seventh letter to Zdeněk Zouhar.

“When looking merely at notation, I myself am often bewildered as to what exactly the song requires and what is the authentic harmonisation.”⁶

Later on, he laments on the sparse use of the sharpened (Lydian) fourth degree of the major scale.

“It is obvious how few composers use, for example, the leap of the VII scale degree and the sharpened fourth, which is more known. Because they do not know about them, and if so, they consider them exceptions, and because from the collections they know they only come to know about harmony of the of the usual I IV scale degree. Even I IV scale degree is little used.”⁷

He ended up keeping the book for seven months before returning it to Zdeněk Zouhar.

3 Milý Příteli: Martinů's letters to Zdeněk Zouhar, edited and annotated by Zdeněk Zouhar and Vít Zouhar, 2008.

4 Martinů's fourth letter to Zdeněk Zouhar dated September 6th 1954 and published in *Milý Příteli: Martinů's letters to Zdeněk Zouhar* by Zdeněk Zouhar and Vít Zouhar, 2008, P. 66/67.

5 Martinů's fourth letter to Zdeněk Zouhar dated September 6th 1954.

6 Martinů's seventh letter to Zdeněk Zouhar dated November 16th 1954. *Milý Příteli*: P. 94/95

7 Martinů's seventh letter to Zdeněk Zouhar dated November 16th 1954. *Milý Příteli*: P. 96/97

The mutual use of the Moravian cadence is indeed an interesting connection between the two giants of Czech music. Janáček's uses the Moravian cadence a total of seven times in the finale of the rhapsodic work *Taras Bulba; III. Proroctví a smrt Tarase Bulby*.

The coda begins on bar 166 and utilises the Moravian cadence in three different four chord transpositions and three shorter three bar statements each in a different transposition.

The first cadence beginning on bar 166 features the chord progression V7c(bIII = V in new key) v-iidominant1 1a-I. The second transposed statement on bar 171 contains vii7-v-iidom1 1a-I leading to the next on bar 176 which uses the chords vii7c-v-iidom1 1d and cadences on I in the key of E major.

In Bar 213, Janáček utilises the solo violin as in the first movement to resemble hopelessness and to depict a fleeting vision of past memories before the end. Bar 221 features rolled sextuplet semiquaver arpeggios in the Harp, these are repeated in bars 224 and 225 leading to a high octave Ab which helps to precede the final cadence that begins on bar 226 and contains the chords V7-v-iidom1 1a and finally I in the key of Db major, which is played in *Grave* tempo and at the dynamic of fortissimo for extra emphasis. This is held for seven beats and signifies the end of the work.

Martinů uses the Moravian cadence as a thematic device (including the octave leap preceding the penultimate chord) and repeats it in its original form a total of 5 times throughout his 6th symphony. This assigns a certain importance of this device which some theorists label as an 'Idée fixe' or as an image of desperation or hope for his, then lost Czechoslovakia. This idea draws it even closer to Hector Berlioz's *Symphonie Fantastique*, which was to be the original title, that Martinů decided to change subsequently. This, which I believe can be called a 'love' connection (or a lament of the lost love of his homeland in Martinů's work), which, in Berlioz's case he attributes to the Irish actress Harriet Smithson, perhaps can be seen in the context of the far relative eighteenth century art form; Irish Aisling poetry (pronounced in Czech as Ašling). In which the poet's homeland is represented by a young, beautiful or conversely an old, haggard woman depending on the fate of the

land and people.

I believe that Martinů utilised this image, whether consciously or unconsciously to depict his feelings and thoughts as an exile towards his homeland under siege, his 'idée fixe' being the land and people of the Czech nation. Through the symphony's free flow form he paints us a fantastic dream of the fate of Czechoslovakia through his eyes and ears.

Further similarities can be found in both works which I will examine here.

The use of Solo Violin in *Fantaisies Symphoniques* can be related to *Taras Bulba* thematically, with both being used to represent fantasy or dream like states of calm or later on in variation; states of frenzy. The Solo Violin features heavily in the assertion of themes, in variation, and with the strings, feature prominently at climactic moments, as in *TB*; for statements of variation and echoing of themes.

In contrast, the thematic use of calm in *Fantaisies Symphoniques* (which I will shorten to *FS*) at the end of each movement is the opposite of *TB* where the end features the death of each of the Three characters (Andrij, Ostap and Taras Bulba) and, as the dramatic content demands a violent statement, it is given, sometimes tinged with hope, often just with bare accentuation.

The common use of interrupting statements in percussion is not solely present in *TB* and can be seen in *FS* also. The percussion called for in *TB* and *FS* are as follows;

TB: Timpani, 5 chromatically arranged Bells, Triangle, Small drum and Cymbals (suspended)

FS: Timpani, Snare drum, Tambourine, Cymbals.

Janáček builds to climaxes and stops them abruptly with crashes of percussion, ending movements and signalling new sections, the use of bells also indicates the beginning and certain characteristics of sections in the music and can largely be seen as form defining.

In connection with Gogol's story he uses cymbals to indicate impending danger or acts of murder. Martinů's use is more textural, however he does begin and accentuate certain sections with percussion, also as a developmental procedure in the more experimental sections of the 2nd movement.

Thus, the importance of *FS* can be seen as more textural and dynamic than rhythmic.

Folk dance like sections in both works point to an enriched cultural awareness, which is quite well known in the works of Janáček, but perhaps not so much in Martinů's work. However, he uses them to great effect in the 2nd movement of *FS*. This also points to a strong rhythmic awareness on Janáček's part and the importance of rhythm in *TB* is a defining factor of the work.

Also, as we saw earlier, the connection between Martinů and rhythmic experimentation and restlessness is very important.

Idiomatic trills in woodwind are common to both works in Mvt. II of *FS* and Mvt. III of *TB* point to a common orchestral sound or orchestrational study but do not indicate a strong influence.

The use of common tonalities is another interesting aspect of Martinu and Janáček's relationship, not just in the use of the Moravian cadence, but in the adaption of folk tunes and the use of the sharpened 4th degree of the scale. Another interesting point is that both works feature no key signature (apart from C major's inherent absence of sharps or flats).

The closest relationship between *FS* and *TB* (*Taras Bulba*) can be found in the second movement of *FS*, with common tonal relationships of key/mode change and harmonic colour. Orchestral use is also a similarity in both works as block orchestral colour and assignment of melody to certain sections is common, however in the hands of Martinů, harmony is more fluid and less goal orientated, he seems to flow around key centres and themes like rivers and reach changes of texture in such a natural way that we can hardly see them coming at all.

Conclusion

Nostalgia can be defined as the idealised yearning for the past, which in Martinů's case can certainly be seen as idealistic. *Fantaisies Symphoniques* however, despite brief closing sections of calm mostly features a turbulent uneasiness which ebbs and flows.

Martinů frequently lamented on the fact that he could not return to Czechoslovakia, preventing this was a stamp on his American passport stating that it must not be used for trips to his homeland, where, less than thirty years previous, he could live and work as a free man.

This must have struck a considerable blow to Martinů's view of the future and of what was in store for his homeland under communist occupation.

However, he certainly was not lonely in America or indeed France or Switzerland, he had his very supportive and caring wife Charlotte with him. She was his anchor and support system who helped him through his darkest times until the end of his life in Switzerland.

Martinů's Symphonic legacy can be viewed in a different light to the rest of his output, I think that the six works can stand alone in terms of quality and originality, that is to say that they are not uniquely singular in his oeuvre but can be given a certain central importance. A constant line of thought which continues from the first to the last shows Martinů's progression as an artist within his influences. From Janáček to Monteverdi, Martinů's capacity to interpret and reinvent the music of his predecessors and even in the case of Ligeti, his contemporaries, shows a composer with a strong place in twentieth century music.

Gustav Mahler once said that 'A symphony must be like the world. It must contain everything.'

I believe that Martinů, through his output, does indeed reflect this point and that his sixth symphony confirms him as a true Czech and artist and reflects his world through his eyes and ears.

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